

Optimization of Power Usage Effectiveness in HPC Data Centers Using a Job Assignment Schedule

Jorge Lozoya Arandia¹, Carlos Jesahel Vega Gómez², Alberto Coronado³, Verónica Lizette Robles Dueñas⁴ and Virgilio Zuñiga Grajeda⁵

¹ School of Engineering and Technological Innovation, University of Guadalajara, Campus Tonalá, Jalisco 45425, Mexico; jorge.larandia@academicos.udg.mx (J.L.-A.)

² School of Engineering and Technological Innovation, University of Guadalajara, Campus Tonalá, Jalisco 45425, Mexico; jesahel.vega@academicos.udg. (A.C)

³ School of Engineering and Technological Innovation, University of Guadalajara, Campus Tonalá, Jalisco 45425, Mexico; mxalberto.coronado@academicos.udg.mx (C.V.G)

⁴ Centro de Analisis de Data y suopercomputo University of Guadalajara, Zapopan Jalisco , Mexico; lizette@redudg.udg.mx (A.C.)

⁵ School of Engineering and Technological Innovation, University of Guadalajara, Campus Tonalá, Jalisco 45425, Mexico; virgilio.zuniga@academicos.udg.mx (V.Z.G)

Abstract. The use of information technologies such as high performance computing (HPC) represents a basic tool for the development of various research and production activities. The data centers in which the HPC equipment is housed represent infrastructure that supports the operation of these technologies, and the optimization of the use of these centers has therefore become a subject of study. HPCs are based on a configuration of many computing nodes in parallel, and during their operation, different capacities are assigned to nodes for data processing; the overhead of assigning tasks to these nodes causes a higher energy consumption by the computer HPC equipment. This article, examine the use of modelling for energy consumption and carry out an optimization analysis to identify factors that generate higher energy consumption. The use of this model allows us to identify how these increase of node during processing, how they cause higher energy consumption and also increase the ambient temperature due to this use of nodes. With the aim of controlling and optimizing these behaviors through modelling, have to analyze how this type of processing and these temperature increases generate variations in energy consumption, and visualized this effect based on the total energy consumption of the data center, measured based on the power usage effectiveness. The conclusions found that the total energy consumption was modified by the processing allocation schedule in these nodes using scheduling jobs assigned to HPC nodes.

Keywords: HPC; Data center; energy simulation; temperature environment; optimization; power usage effectiveness (PUE).

1 Introduction

High performance computing (HPC) involves the arrangement of a large number of computing nodes that can work together to process large amounts of data through the use of numerous cores interconnected by low latency data networks and large amounts of memory. The data center hosting these systems is of vital importance in terms of their operation and to ensure the availability, integrity, and confidentiality of the data that are processed. These data centers generally operate with an annual availability of 99.99% per year, or offer a Service Level Agreement (SLA) with high levels of availability, which represents a high energy consumption. Research has estimated that data centers worldwide account for 1.1–1.5% of global electricity use [4-5]. A data center for HPC typically involves a large number of computing nodes, each consisting of multiple processing cores [4]. The total consumption of energy in these HPC data centers is an important issue, and many researchers have studied this topic and contributed to optimizing the total cost of consumption. Power consumption by data centers is extremely large, and it is anticipated that it will continue to increase in the future [1].

In view of the high number of servers required to support the computing nodes, the storage, network, and air conditioning systems, and the technological evolution that will allow for the development of new types of infrastructure for the center, analysis and modelling can provide information for decision-making to future implementations in HPC data centers that are already in operation and for the design process of new HPC data centers. The size and performance of these systems continue to increase, causing concerns over their growing energy requirements [6-9]. In the case of data centers that host HPC, the operational dynamics responds to the levels of use required by the jobs that are executed. The allocation of nodes is carried out by different types of control software that assign resources as required; this is done by generating work queues that allow jobs to be organized and run in the most efficient way in terms of using all of the available processing capacity. That is, nodes are dynamically assigned to different jobs to maximize the use of the HPC nodes in the high performance computer. The processing task assigned to the HPC nodes generates a behavior with patterns of use that could be improved from the point of view of energy consumption. Servers in these data centers are underutilized due to over-provisioning, which contributes heavily towards the high power consumption of the data centers [4]. Thus, an important priority when using HPC is to avoid the over-provisioning of equipment. One technique that is commonly employed to optimize the use of these centers involves producing a smart schedule of jobs to assign the use of computing nodes. A batch job schedule periodically monitors the status of computing resources in a cluster and distributes jobs efficiently [14]. The job schedule organizes all the resources available for HPC, such as processing, memory, storage and networks, and assigns jobs to the user based on patterns of use that are determined by the system administrator.

To define the energy required by a data center in order to fulfil the SLA, the other factor that is analyzed in this paper is the temperature in the data center environment. When calculating the total energy consumption by data centers, this metric should be included in the list of sensors that report the status of the data center in real time. One of the factors that causes higher energy consumption is the use of air conditioning, which

accounts for 30–40% of the electricity consumption of the data center [3]. When the jobs assignment requires more processing from the information technology (IT) equipment that support the HPC nodes the temperature can undergo variations, it is unclear how the whether air conditioning causes an increase or a decrease in the total energy consumption when the use of HPC nodes varies.

This article analyses how the use of processing can be tied in with the optimization of energy consumption, with a focus on the effect of the schedule of jobs on the machine environment, and with the aim of achieving an improved total annual consumption PUE by considering these variables affecting power use and consumption. The use of processing in the HPC nodes can be evaluated to support the energy-saving measures implemented in the server room, to create a model that evaluates the energy-saving effects [1]. Our linear processing analysis provides an approximate result and uses a classification Table [2].

2 Energy consumption model in data centers

An analysis of the energy consumption by HPC data centers can be carried out by modelling this consumption and identifying the factors that affect it. The possibility of its optimization depends on the approach used to identify these input variables and the correct analysis of the output values. This article examine the factors affecting processing and the heat generation in the environment due to normal HPC operation, as these factors can be changed via the HPC node usage schedule and are reflected in the total energy consumption. When the analyses divide the factors affecting energy consumption into two types: the first is the effect of the temperature of the environment and how variations are generated by an increase in demand for processing (Figure 1), and the second is the scheduling of the job assigned to processes for each node as they are reflected in the PUE of the data center.

Figure 1. Number of cores used compared with energy consumption in kVA (kilovolt-ampere), versus the amount of cooling (TR) used per hour.

The energy consumption model of a data center is regulated by different metrics developed by different companies known as the Green Grid, which have generated a series of recommendations and best practices for energy efficiency and sustainability, such as

controlling CO2 emissions [2]. These measures generate different indices of measures known as the PUE. The calculation is carried out by adding the energy consumption by all the data center facilities to obtain the overall energy consumption of the IT equipment. The closer the value of this index to 1.0, the better the efficiency of the equipment [10]. This work, use a HPC data center model with a PUE of 2.3 and examined the distribution of energy consumption. with PUE = 2.3 The PUE calculation for the HPC data center considers the variables affecting the IT equipment, such as the consumption due to processing by the computing nodes, the use of air conditioning and lighting, the losses of the inverter in the UPS (uninterruptible power source) and others. These values are a sum of energy consumed and the energy losses to give the total energy consumed, and are divided by the power used by the IT equipment, as shown in Equation (1). A ton of refrigeration (TR) is a unit that is often used as a general indicator of the capacity or size of a refrigeration plant. It is defined as the rate of heat transfer for freezing (or melting) 1 ton (2,000 lb.; 907 kg) of pure ice at 0 °C (32 F) over 24 hours [2].

$$PUE = \frac{\text{Total energy (IT equipment + air conditioning + lighting + UPS losses in inverters + others)}}{\text{Energy used by IT equipment}} \quad (1)$$

Table 1. Power consumption by the HPC data center per year, as used in the PUE calculations

Power consumption by the HPC data center per year in kW	
Air conditioning	105.64
IT	103.24
Lighting	19.21
UPS losses	12.00
Total consumption	240.08

$$PUE = \frac{(103.24 + 105.64 + 19.21 + 12)}{103.24} = 2.33 \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) shows that the effectiveness of the HPC data center is 2.33.

The HPC data center for which analysed the behaviour of the PUE was made up of 150 processing nodes and had a performance of 504 teraflops (504 billion operations per second). This equipment assigns processes in parallel, and the use per node is monitored. The HPC equipment carries out a process in parallel using all the nodes that are assigned to each job. The process is monitored and generates a total consumption for each node per hour, which allows us to visualise how many nodes are in use in each

hour, based on the allocation of jobs by the monitoring software. The HPC data center used for this analysis has nodes with 36 cores per CPU. Figure 2 shows a graph of the use of each node per hour in a HPC center, the number of central processing units (CPUs) used in the job processing, used per hour.

Figure 2. CPUs used per hour.

To analyse the relationship between the environmental temperature and node use, it has used the monitored increase in ambient temperature and its relationship with the energy consumption per hour. The TR number was monitored with reference to the total energy consumption of the HPC data center, as shown in Figure 3. This analysis of the behaviour of the temperature was carried out in the data center for a month, generating an average per day as shown in Figure 3. This average daily consumption allowed for a comparison with the energy consumption due to the use of air conditioning in the data center, and statistical values was estimated for one year of operation and processing [7]. The data center used for the measurements for this article was the Data Analysis and Supercomputing Center (CADS) at the University of Guadalajara; this is an HPC data center with precision air conditioning that houses a Leo Átrox supercomputer consisting of 150 processing nodes homogeneous connected whit a fiber of 100gbps. The data collected are used by the climate monitoring system and resource management software.

Figure 3. Amount of cooling in TR versus the total energy consumption of the HPC data center per hour.

The use of PUE in many cases relates to the minimum consumption of energy cited [37]. This article, seek to identify how an analysis of the maximum and minimum consumption can be used to optimise the energy consumption through the control of the energy demand of the HPC processing nodes, due to consumption factors in air conditioning and its realisation with the HPC process.

3 Analysis of power consumption by HPC nodes

The increase in the use of air conditioning as the use of processing increases is a behaviour that has been analysed in several previous articles. In energy consumption optimisation analysis, it has been observed that processing generates variations in the ambient temperature, meaning that the energy consumption varies. Due to the increasing power density, minimisation of the heat produced by HPC processing and thermal management are important for data centers, in order to increase the lifetime of servers and to reduce economic losses in the form of electricity bills [11]. Energy efficiency has a direct effect on the efficiency of computer node usage.

Data processing in HPC is assigned by processing nodes. These nodes contain a large number of CPUs that are interconnected via different types of software that assign the processing required for each task. Energy consumption per node is defined using the cores that make up each node. Monitoring the use of each node allows us to observe how each node behaves as it is assigned the processing job during each minute of processing (Figure 4). This information allows us to determine the number of jobs assigned per node. Our analysis of the use of the nodes of the HPC data center for this article was based on the average use of processing per node, determined based on the time for which is used. This average is made up of the sum of the amount of processing assimilated to the cores that make up each node and is displayed on the percentage of the node used in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Average load off jobs processing. Node monitoring compared to idle time every 15 minutes.

The power consumption of a task is measured based on the processor power consumed [12]. Once the energy consumption per processing job capacity has been determined, it is compared with the thermal change resulting from the operation of the HPC node processing, and this relationship allows us to observe the change in consumption by the IT equipment and the stabilisation of the consumption due to air conditioning (Figure 5).

In Figure 5, see a comparison where it allows us to contrast the use of processing with the air conditioning provided at the time that it is making use of this processing, in it you can identify the behaviour of energy consumption related to the air conditioning used and the amount of HPC processing per hour. This allows us to identify the direct relationship between the energy demand and the processing and air conditioning consumption in TR per hour of operation of the HPC data center.

Figure 5. Comparison of energy consumption with the number of processing nodes used, and its effects on the thermal impact per hour of work

The use of HPC resources, which is based on the assignment of jobs to the HPC nodes, has a direct effect on the energy consumption in the HPC data center. This can be visualised based on the number of cores used per job and the effect on the ambient temperature. It was observed that the number of jobs processed per node directly affected both the thermal conditions and the total energy consumption (Figure 5). The use of processing jobs in the HPC nodes was identified according to the allocation of jobs per node, and each submitted process was queued, with processes waiting for resources to be released for use. These resources were assigned by the administrator; however, this assignment did not depend on the number of nodes used but the number of nodes assigned. To configure the cluster environment and manage batch jobs, the scheduler was chosen to reflect the characteristics of the computation environment from the perspective of both software and hardware [15].

The task of assigning jobs is based on how the system runs the jobs. When those jobs finish, the nodes become free to take new ones, which are waiting for their turn to use the infrastructure. Some research has focused on using this scheduling to optimise the processing time and hence to improve the availability of the HPC resources [14]. In this case, is used a variable that allowed us to determine the number of resources that the job was going to need, and thus to determine the precedence of use and to force a constant number of nodes use. The assignment of processing nodes for HPC without a schedule to optimise the energy consumption allows for the random allocation of jobs to the nodes. Figure 6 shows how different jobs requiring different numbers of nodes are assigned and how they make use of the resources without an order, that can control the energy demand. Each job has a certain amount of resources, and new jobs are assigned to be used only considering the free HPC nodes. The assigned jobs shown in Figure 6 represent the average usage per hour of each node; you can see that Job 1 requires a high number of nodes and this use is not maintained, showing a big space off

free nodes until the next time the resources are required, whereas Jobs 4 and 8 are more stable in terms of the number of nodes used.

Figure 6. Jobs assigned to nodes without a processing schedule.

When generating a processing scheduler, a variable is incorporated that assigns the shift of the job according to the number of processors required for its execution and the time required. These resource allocation variables allow a use off HPC processing nodes grows and decreases in a synchronous form, meaning that the energy consumption of the IT infrastructure of the HPC system can be controlled.

The way in which jobs are scheduled has a direct effect on the assignment and use of the cores, which determine the energy consumption and can be used to give a more stable pattern of energy use. Figure 8 shows the number of c- the HPC nodes cores assigned per hour are more stable. In this way, you can manage the energy demand and make the processing demand more consistent. You can see how allocating HPC nodes using a scheduler allows for stable computer usage and smaller changes in the large amounts of computer usage and power consumption required.

Figure 8. Use of cores with a processing scheduler.

The job schedule has a direct effect on the assignment of nodes and the use of the cores, thus determining the energy consumption and providing a more stable pattern of energy consumption (Figure 8) because the consumption is the same during more time. This behaviour is based on the contents of the jobs. Each job has different characteristics that require the cores to be used in different ways and with different timings. The assignment of jobs allows the machine to give better performance and imposes less physical wear. The alignment of jobs during different hours of the day allows a schedule to predict the energy consumption the case of the temperature of the environment and the use of air conditioning (Figure 9).

The schedule of each job can be assigned to a different node that holds the request and the preceding resource is assigned based on the state of each node (Table 2). The way in which the job is assigned is based on the status and use of the node, that means the state of the node assignment.

Table 2. Node assignment per state for an HPC data center

PARTITION	AVAIL	FIMELI		STATE	NODELIST
		MIT	NODES		
DEFQ*	up	infinite	64	down*	020,031-054,071-100,112,139],cnf[143-144]
DEFQ*	up	infinite	25	comp	013,018-019,026-027,067-070,101-102,109-110]
DEFQ*	up	infinite	1	drain	nv01 4-017,028-030,055-066,103-108,11,123-137],
DEFQ*	up	infinite	47	alloc	cnf[141-142],phi[01-04]
DEFQ*	up	infinite	1	idle	
DEFQ*	up	infinite	2	down*	cn[137-138]
DEFQ*	up	infinite	1	drain	cn140,nvd02
DEFQ*	up	infinite	1	down*	nvd01
DEFQ*	up	infinite	8	down*	nvd02
DEFQ*	up	infinite	1	idel	nvd04
DEFQ*	up	infinite	1	down*	cn[115-122]

The node processing schedule is visualised as a single energy consumption and allows for stable energy demand, as it's shown in Figure 9, the joint jobs per hour aligned according to the node demand for the schedule applied in the HPC processing. In this case, the priorities assigned to the processes were defined as shown in Table 2, and the resulting numbers of jobs per hour are displayed in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Usage schedule showing the numbers of nodes with jobs per hour.

Once a job has been assigned, it will have different time requirements depending on the use of the node and the preceding jobs have used . This describe the numbers of nodes required for each job per partition.

The job schedule assigns nodes per use of processing and can be reloaded according to the schedule assignment. This process works with time limit assignments that can be inferred from the job assignment (as shown in Figure 10).

Figure 10. Data job assignment and reprocessing schedule for HPC nodes.

The allocation of nodes using a scheduler considers the different stages of the HPC process and identifies the required resources with the aim of achieving the most stable

use of the equipment. Initially, an allocation of nodes is generated based on the requirements of the work to be processed. Once the number of nodes required has been determined, the nodes are scheduled to use the platform. At this point, jobs are queued to await the release of nodes for use. When nodes become available, processing begins, and the node assignment is subject to a time limit. When the results have been delivered, the processing cycle terminates and frees the nodes to be reassigned. There is then the option to either finish the process or return it for reprocessing, which involves waiting for processing nodes resources to become available, in order to maintain control over processing and avoid increases in uncontrolled processing and high energy consumption due to these. If the work is considered to be complete, the results are delivered, and if reprocessing is required at this point, the job is returned for allocation by the scheduler. The schedule assigns the nodes in a way that, as soon as it is determined that the time limit frees the nodes for reuse, it must return to waiting for an agenda that optimizes the energy and cooling demand of the HPC data center. The procedure described above is shown in Figure 10.

4 Results

The scheduled processes were assigned to the supercomputer housed in the data center, both with and without a resource assignment scheduler. The hourly behaviour was observed and compared based on the TR of the environment and the total energy consumption of the data center. The first result shows that the processing usage had a direct effect on energy consumption, and that the air conditioning usage in TR increases as the processing increased (Figure 11). When the usage associated with processing jobs did not increase in a stable manner, the power air conditioning TR usage changed in the same way.

Figure 11. Process operation of HPC nodes without the use of a schedule, compared with the air conditioning capacity in TR and the total energy consumption of the data center in kW.

Figure 12. Process operation of HPC nodes with the use of a schedule, compared with the air conditioning capacity in TR and the total energy consumption of the data center in kW.

Figure 12 shows that a more stable processing schedule generated a more stable behaviour in terms of energy use for air conditioning and overall energy consumption. Being able to assign processes in a staggered manner with stable growth allowed the same stability in the energy consumption factors related to the use of air conditioning to be achieved.

Table 4. PUE for the HPC data center

Job asigment	Projection PUE in HPC data Center
With job scheduling	4.44
Without job scheduling	4.65

In this annual consumption projection, the PUE improves with a value closer to one. Our analysis of the factors affecting this value showed that the energy efficiency was increased by reducing instabilities in the processing and the use of air conditioning. Our results are based on projections of energy consumption behaviour under the same conditions for one year. In addition, this article compare two different processing data days in the scheduling agenda of nodes this method can be used to determine the consistency of the behaviour of the PUE factors.

5 Conclusions

The energy consumption in a HPC data center generally behaves in the same way as in a non-specialised data center. However, due to its architecture, the behaviour of the

HPC data center infrastructure can be modified due to the nature of its processing nodes use and how these behaviours affect its energy consumption.

The modification of specific variables, such as the schedule of processing jobs to the general energy consumption nodes of the HPC data center, can be used to optimise the PUE of the HPC data center. The projected values for the HPC data center were $PUE = 4.65$ without a process schedule, and $PUE = 4.44$ with a process schedule, meaning that some variation could be perceived in the energy consumption.

The energy efficiency (PUE) of a data center is considerably improved when a scheduler is used to allocate processes to nodes, and it is noted in a considerable way in the amount of HPC processing (figure 15). In the same way, the changes in the environment due to a more stable demand for processing can reduce the amount of cooling required. This reduces the waste and costs associated with maintenance, as well as the costs arising from the total energy consumption. Similarly, the wear and tear on the HPC processing equipment is reduced when these temperature changes are minimised. Figure 16 shows this behaviour, and it can be seen that the results are consistent in the two different tests of different job assignment processing works that have different characteristics, but which were processed with and without schedules.

When generating a scheduler for the usage of the nodes, it was observed that the increases in processing consumption could be controlled, meaning that the heat generated could also be controlled in increments or decrements based on the usage of the nodes. In this way, the use of air conditioning could also be controlled to maintain the ambient temperature within the data center and to give a more stable energy consumption pattern in which consumption peaks are avoided, as shown in Figure 11.

Overall, by using more processing and increasing the temperature, the energy demand of the data center can be controlled, and the energy consumption of the data center can be optimised based on this schedule of allocation of processing, depending on how gradual increases and decreases in the energy demand of the data center are achieved. In this article, a processing schedule structure is proposed for HPC that allows these variables to be controlled, the control of the operation factors such as processing schedule have direct influence the control over the energy demand of the entire data center based on the use of air conditioning, which is one of the most important factors affecting the energy consumption of the data center (Figure 12).

It is evident that the use of air conditioning and the equipment associated with its operation continue to offer opportunities for improving energy consumption. However, using these scales of analysis to take advantage of HPC processing assignment by a schedule, allows the associated costs for energy demand to be reflected in a greater use of processing.

References

1. Aksanli, B.; Rosing, T. Providing regulation services and managing data center peak power budgets. In Proceedings of the 2014 Design, Automation & Test in Europe Conference & Exhibition (DATE), Dresden, Germany, 24–28 March 2014; pp. 143–147.
2. Benini, L.; Micheli, G.D. System-level power optimization: Techniques and tools. *ACM Trans. Des. Autom. Electron. Syst. (Todaes)* 2000, 5, 115–192.
3. Berl, A.; Gelenbe, E.; Di Girolamo, M. Energy-efficient cloud computing. *Comp. J.* 2010, 53, 1045–1051. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
4. Bogdan, P.; Garg, S.; Ogras, U.Y. Energy-efficient computing from systems-on-chip to micro-server and data centers. In Proceedings of the 2015 Sixth International Green Computing Conference and Sustainable Computing Conference (IGSC), Las Vegas, NV, USA, 14–16 December 2015; pp. 1–6.
5. Brown, K.; Bouley, D. Classification of data center infrastructure management (DCIM) tools. In Schneider Electric’s Data Center, White Paper; Science Center: Foxboro, MA, USA, 2014. [Google Scholar]
6. Buyya, R.; Beloglazov, A.; Abawajy, J. Energy-efficient management of data center resources for cloud computing: A vision, architectural elements, and open challenges. 2010. Available online: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1006.0308> (accessed on 9 April 2015).
7. CADS- UdeG. (2018). Data Analysis Center of the University of Guadalajara.
8. Demetriou, D.; Calder, A. Evolution of data center infrastructure management tools. *ASHRAE J.* 2019, 61, 52–58. [Google Scholar]
9. Eric, M.; Arman, S.; Nuoa, L.; Sarah, S.; Jonathan, K. Recalibrating global data center energy-use estimates, American Association for the Advancement of Science. *Science* 2020, 367, 984–986. [Google Scholar]
10. Feitelson D.G., Rudolph L., Schwiegelshohn U., Sevcik K.C., Wong P. (1997) Theory and practice in parallel job scheduling. In: Feitelson D.G., Rudolph L., Eds., *Job Scheduling Strategies for Parallel Processing. JSSPP 1997. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 1291. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-63574-2_14
11. Futawatari, N.; Udagawa, Y.; Mori, T.; Hayama, H. Improving prediction accuracy concerning the thermal environment of a data center by using design of experiments. *Energies* 2020, 13, 4595.
12. Garday, D.; Housley, J. Thermal storage system provides emergency data center cooling; Intel Corporation: Santa Clara, CA, USA, 2007. [Google Scholar]
13. Germán, R.; Carlos, B. Validation of calibrated energy models: Common errors. *Energies* 2017, 10, 1587. [Google Scholar]
14. Halawa, M.S.; Díaz Redondo, R.P.; Fernández Vilas, A. Unsupervised KPIs-based clustering of jobs in HPC data centers. *Sensors* 2020, 20, 4111.
15. Jian, L.; Jakub, J.; Hailong, L.; Wen-Quan, T.; Yuanyuan, D.; Jinyue, Y. A new indicator for a fair comparison on the energy performance of data centers. *Appl. Energy* 2020, 276, 115497. [Google Scholar]
16. Koomey, J. Growth in data center electricity use 2005 to 2010. In a report by Analytical Press, completed at the request of the New York Times; Analytics Press: Burlingame, CA, USA, 2011. [Google Scholar]
17. Lin, P.; Zhang, S.; Van Gilde, J. Data center temperature rise during a cooling system outage. In Schneider Electric’s Data Center, White Paper; Science Center: Foxboro, MA, USA, 2013. [Google Scholar]

18. Christodoulou G., Gourvès L., Pascual F. Scheduling selfish tasks: About the performance of truthful algorithms. In: G. Lin, Ed., *Computing and Combinatorics. COCOON 2007. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 4598. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-73545-8_20
19. Mamun, S.A.; Gilday, A.; Singh, A.K.; Ganguly, A.; Merrett, G.V.; Wang, X.; Al-Hashimi, B.M. Intra- and inter-server smart task scheduling for profit and energy optimization of hpc data centers. *J. Low Power Electron. Appl.* 2020, 10, 32.
20. Mehdi, M.; Mostafa, R.; Hamid, S. Temperature-aware power consumption modeling in hyperscale cloud data centers. *Future Gener. Comput. Syst.* 2019, 94, 130–139. [Google Scholar]
21. Niemann, J.; Brown, K.; Avelar, V. Impact of hot and cold aisle containment on data center temperature and efficiency. In *Schneider Electric's Data Center, White Paper*; Science Center: Foxboro, MA, USA, 2017. [Google Scholar]
22. Renugadevi, T.; Geetha, K.; Muthukumar, K.; Geem, Z.W. Optimized energy cost and carbon emission-aware virtual machine allocation in sustainable data centers. *Sustainability* 2020, 12, 6383.
23. Rodero, I.; Jaramillo, J.; Quiroz, A.; Parashar, M.; Guim, F.; Poole, S. Energy-efficient application-aware online provisioning for virtualized clouds and data centers. In *Proceedings of the International Green Computing Conference (IGCC)*, Chicago, IL, USA, 15–18 August 2010; pp. 31–45.
24. Santos, A.F.; Gaspar, P.D.; Souza, H.J.L. New data center performance index: Perfect design data center—PDD. *Climate* 2020, 8, 110.
25. Sasakura, K.; Aoki, T.; Komatsu, M.; Watanabe, T.A. Temperature-risk and energy-saving evaluation model for supporting energy-saving measures for data center server rooms. *Energies* 2020, 13, 5222.